

Kalighat Temple

By Liwen Liu, University of Toronto

Entry tags: Religious Group, Shaktism, Religious Place, Shrine, Hinduism

Kalighat Temple is a Hindu temple situated in Kolkata, West Bengal, India. The temple name is a Bengali compound made of Kālī—the name of a Hindu goddess—and ghāṭ—the landing stage of a river. Kalighat temple, conforming to the name “the landing stage of Kālī”, is situated beside the Adi Ganga River, the old course of Hooghly river, which is an eastern distributary of the sacred Ganges. The Kalighat Temple is dedicated to the Hindu goddess Kālī, a powerful goddess associated with time, death, and destruction in Śakti tradition. Kālī is also considered an incarnation of goddess Satī, whose myth gives sanctity to the Kalighat Temple. It's widely believed that the right toes of Satī fell in the position of Kalighat, and the relics of Satī's body are alleged to be found in the Kundupukur tank of the Kalighat Temple. Due to this connection with the myth, Kalighat is listed among the fifty-one śaktipīthas (seats of goddesses), which are pilgrimage sites for goddess worship. Built in the 19th century, Kalighat Temple is a temple complex that hosts not only Kālī, but also Śiva, Rādhā-Kṛṣṇa, and other local goddesses of Bengal. Nowadays, thousands of devotees visit the Kalighat Temple daily to worship and receive the grace of goddess Kālī. As one of the religious centers of Kolkata, Kalighat attracts pilgrims from all over West Bengal and India. In addition to its religious importance, Kalighat Temple is also a thriving economic body, depending on which thousands of sevāyets (temple proprietors), pāṇḍās (priests), shop owners, hawkers, and beggars earn a living. Kalighat Temple is well-known for its animal sacrifice. Goat sacrifice, namely pāthābali in Bengali, is performed daily in the temple. One goat is sacrificed every day at noon as the midday meal for goddess Kālī, who is pleased by offerings of blood and flesh. In addition to this regular daily sacrifice, more goats are immolated if devotees come to make goat offerings. Buffalos are also sacrificed during the Durga Puja. The sacrificial violence strongly contradicts the non-violence upheld in mainstream Hinduism, attracting wide criticism from orthodox Hindus, vegetarians, animal lovers, and modernizers. Despite controversies incurred within the Hindu tradition and in the public sphere, animal sacrificial is still performed today as a living tradition in Kalighat Temple, providing an example of how the sacrificial killing prescribed in the medieval scripture Kālikā Purāṇa is performed in contemporary practices.

Date Range: 19 CE - 21 CE

Region: Kalighat Kali Temple

Region tags: Asia, South Asia, India

Kalighat Temple is situated in Kolkata (formerly Calcutta), West Bengal, India.

参与者地位

✓ 精英 ✓ 宗教专家 ✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

一般变量

来源与发掘

书面资料来源

用以理解这个题目的书面资料来源

- 来源1: Moodie, D. (2019). *The making of a modern temple and a Hindu city: Kalighat and Kolkata*. Oxford University Press.
- 来源2: Basu Roy, I. (1993). *Kalighat, its impact on socio-cultural life of Hindus*. Gyan Pub. House.
- 来源3: Gupta, S. (2003). *The Domestication of a Goddess: Caraṇa-tīrtha Kālīghāṭ, the Mahāpīṭha of Kālī*. (Rachel McDermott Fell, Jeffrey Kripal J, Ed.), *Encountering Kālī: In the Margins, at the Center, in the West*. Berkeley, Calif.: University of California Press.

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE
Region: West Bengal

在线来源

用以理解这个题目的在线来源

- 来源1 URL: <https://web.archive.org/web/20030630031321/http://www.hindu.com/thehindu/fr/2003/05/09/stories/2003050901460>;
- 来源1 描述: Balakrishnan, S (9 May 2003). "Kali Mandir of Kolkata". The Hindu.
- 来源2 URL: <https://kalighatkalitemple.com/>
- 来源2 描述: The official website of Kalighat Temple

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE
Region: West Bengal

这个地方曾经是发掘重点吗（古代、违法的、科学的）？

给每个年代或者发掘类型回答‘是’

— 否

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE
Region: West Bengal

地形背景

地点是否与景点要素相关联

— 水体（与来源不同）

Notes: Kundupukur, the tank of Kalighat Temple, is believed to connect to a subterranean distributary of the sacred Ganges river.

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE
Region: West Bengal

除了结构之外，这个地方是否涉及人造特征：

其他特征可能包括空地，梯田，当地环境的其他整改。

— 否

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE
Region: West Bengal

这个地方是否位于城市或显著城市化的地区：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

这个地方和城市结构之间是否有明显的界限：

—是

Notes: The temple wall separates the temple complex from the surroundings and the markets around the temple.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

这个地方是否明显位于城市结构中：

这个地方是否位于中心位置，或重要通道的十字路口？

—是

Notes: The temple is close to the subway station and the bus stop named "Kalighat". The district in which the Kalighat temple is situated is named after the temple as "Kalighat".

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

这个地方是否在乡村的环境中：

—否

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

这个地方是否远离非宗教的居住地点：

—否

Notes: Kalighat Temple is situated in a lively market, which is always crowded with people looking for street food and pūjā items (items for worship, such as incense, beads, and candles). A few blocks from the temple, there is also a neighborhood of idol-makers who make and sell idols, and clothes and ornamentations used to decorate idols.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

结构存在

是否有结构/特征表现：

说明：对每个结构/特征或群组的答案可以不同。

—是

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 单一结构

— 否

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 单一特征

— 其他【请注明】: A flat space in the city.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 一组结构 :

— 是

Notes: Kalighat Temple is a temple complex consisting of a main temple that hosts the goddess Kālī, a Rādhā-Kṛṣṇa Temple for Rādhā-Kṛṣṇa, a Natmondir—a rectangular platform in which devotees sing evening prayers, a Sosthi Tala—an altar on which three mother goddess are worship, a Harkatha Tala—a sacrificial pavilion for animal sacrifice, and two kitchens in which food offerings for deities are prepared.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 它们是否是单一设计/施工阶段的一部分 :

— 否

Notes: The construction of Kalighat Temple was initiated in 1799 and completed in 1809. The Sosthi Tala was constructed in 1880. The Rādhā-Kṛṣṇa Temple was constructed in 1843, and a Dolmancho was added to it in 1858.

Reference: Basu Roy, Indrani. Kalighat, Its Impact on Socio-cultural Life of Hindus. New Delhi: Gyan Publishing House, n.d.. p.pp.1-14

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 一组特征 :

— 否

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 它是一个更大地方/圣所的一部分

— 否

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 结构/特征或者群组的功能是什么：
给每一个明显的功能回答一次“是”

— 崇拜

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 崇拜：

—其他【请注明】：Both communal and individual worships are performed in the temple.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

— 献祭的

Notes: Goat sacrifice is performed daily at noon. Buffalo sacrifice is performed during Durga Puja.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 结构/特征是否完成：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 结构/特征是否计划持续超过一代：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 结构/特征是否随时间而改变：

— 是

Notes: There is no major change in the overall temple structure, but renovations happen throughout time. For example, Harkath Tala, the sacrificial pavilion, was enclosed by a wall that is only four-foot high. In 2006, a seven-foot wall was established to conceal the bloody scene of killing.

Reference: Moodie, Deonnie. *The Making of a Modern Temple and a Hindu City: Kalighat and Kolkata*. Oxford University Press, n.d.. p.143

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 结构/特征是否被摧毁 :

— 否

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 结构/特征是否被重建

— 否

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

创作/建构/奉献的原因

这个地方是否被用于对非人类超自然存在的崇拜/沟通 :

— 是

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 致力于一种超自然的存在 :

— 否

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 致力于多于一种的超自然存在 :

— 是【请注明】 : The main shrine is dedicated to goddess Kālī. Within the temple complex, there are also other small shrines in which Śiva, Ṣaṣṭhī Mā, Rāthā-Kṛṣṇa, and other deities are worshiped. Śiva is the consort of Satī, another form of the goddess Kālī. Three local goddesses—Ṣaṣṭhī, Sītala, and Chandī—are worshipped as three stones placed on an altar. Rāthā and Kṛṣṇa are hosted at the shrine in the west of the main temple. Because Rāthā and Kṛṣṇa are vegetarian Vaiṣṇava deities, their food offerings are prepared in a separate kitchen.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

这个地方是用来崇拜半神人类的吗 :

— 否

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

这个地方是用来崇拜非神祖先的吗？

— 否

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

这个地方是由一个官方政体委托建造/建造的吗：

政体是一个利用劳动力的地方权力机制。

— 否

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

结构是由特定组群的人建造的吗：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

此地被认为起源于神圣干涉的结果：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

这个地方是被创造用于标记或纪念一个超自然存在或者人类的诞生地吗：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

此地是作为一个事件的结果被创造的吗：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

注明

—其他【请注明】：Myth

Notes: The sanctity of Kalighat derives from the myth of goddess Satī, which is mentioned in several purāṇas popular in eastern India, such as the the Kālikā Purāṇa and the Devī Bhagavata Purāṇa. In the myth, Satī committed suicide in sacrificial fire because her father Dakṣa humiliated her husband Śiva. Śiva, grieving over the death of his beloved wife, carried her body and roamed around the world. Satī's body was scattered and fell on more than fifty places, which are known as śakti pīṭhas. It's believed that the right toes of Satī fell in the Kundupukur tank of Kalighat. Therefore, the myth makes Kalighat a sacred place in Śakti tradition.

Reference: Basu Roy, Indrani. Kalighat, Its Impact on Socio-cultural Life of Hindus. New Delhi: Gyan Publishing House, n.d.. p.pp.15-19

Reference: Moodie, Deonnie. The Making of a Modern Temple and a Hindu City: Kalighat and Kolkata. Oxford University Press, n.d.. p.49-57

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

此地的创立是否由外部资金或者物质捐助：

— 是

Notes: The construction of the temple was sponsored by the Sabarna Roy Choudhury family, who are the local landholders (zamindars) of Kolkata.

Reference: Basu Roy, Indrani. Kalighat, Its Impact on Socio-cultural Life of Hindus. New Delhi: Gyan Publishing House, n.d.. p.3

Reference: Moodie, Deonnie. The Making of a Modern Temple and a Hindu City: Kalighat and Kolkata. Oxford University Press, n.d.. p.172, n.7

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

对于同一个宗教团体/传统的赞助是否作为此地的主要用法：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

此地的建设是否由以下因素促动：

— 期待荣宠作为回报

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

此地特别为存放经典/神经经准备的吗：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

设计和材料依然存在

整体结构

这个地方是否由多重结构组成：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 任何结构附属于风景或者于风景特征相关联吗：

— 是

Notes: A tank named Kundupukur is situated southeast of the temple outside the boundary. The water of the tank is believed to be associated with the Adi Ganga, the distributary of the sacred Ganges river. The water is turbid, and three attempts to cleanse the tank—made respectively in 1871, 1887, and 1981—failed. The failure seems to prove its subterranean connection with the Ganges. It is believed that the right toes of Sati fell into this tank, thus, the water is sacred and powerful in granting the boon of a child to women.

Reference: Basu Roy, Indrani. Kalighat, Its Impact on Socio-cultural Life of Hindus. New Delhi: Gyan Publishing House, n.d.. p.p.13

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 任何结构附属于其他结构吗：

— 是

Notes: An over-bridge connects the main temple with the kitchen, so the meat offering (bhog) for Kālī can be directly sent to the inner sanctum.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 在结构中有阶级吗：

— 是

Notes: The main temple, which hosts the image of Kālī, is higher in hierarchy, and is the highest among the temple structures.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

纪念建筑存在吗：

在这里，纪念性建筑被定义为超过平均人类比例的建筑结构，并且通常比实现结构的实用功能所需的更大且更复杂。纪念碑建筑的例子包括美索不达米亚金字塔，埃及金字塔，希腊和罗马神庙，中美洲金字塔，北美和爱琴海墓葬等。

— 否

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

结构/特征由自然材料组成吗：

针对每个材料类型回答【是】

—否

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

结构/特征由人工材料组成吗：

—是【请注明】：Clay bricks and terracotta. The wall that demarcates the temple boundary is made of cement.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

装饰

装饰存在吗

—否

Notes: Kalighat temple is a typical chala-style temple, which resembles thatch-roofed huts in rural Bengal. The roof is decorated in color. It's believed that the top stick is made of gold.

Reference: Basu Roy, Indrani. Kalighat, Its Impact on Socio-cultural Life of Hindus. New Delhi: Gyan Publishing House, n.d.. p.2-3

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

标志

这个地方有标志性的明显的特征吗：

—是

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

眼睛（是否风格化）

—是

Notes: The icon features three wide, red eyes. The third eye shows that she is related to Śiva, the three-eyed one (Trinetra). Although Kālī is a goddess without a consort, she is considered an incarnation of Śiva's wife Satī. The color of the red eye conforms to the Kālīkā Purāṇa (8.10), which describes Kālī as the one with red eyes (āraktanayanā).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 超自然存在 (动物化)

— 否

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 超自然存在 (地球形状的)

— 否

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 超自然存在 (拟人化的)

— 是

Notes: The icon of Kālī in Kalighat Temple is a piece of black, oval stone with three red eyes, and a protruding golden tongue. She has four hands. The upper right hand is in abhaya mudrā, the gesture of no fear, and the lower right hand is in varada mudrā, the gesture of granting wishes. On the left side, the upper hand holds a sword, and the lower hand holds a severed human head. The body of the icon is covered with a Saree, which is regularly changed throughout the year. The iconology conforms to the portrait of Kālī in the Kālikā Purāṇa (8.9-11): “Seeing Kālikā standing upon a lion, black, breasts full and high, with four arms, a sweet mouth, holding a blue lotus, auspicious, (9) giving varada and abhaya, a sword in her hand, provided with all qualities, her eyes some-what red, lovely unloosened hair, enchanting, (10) then Dakṣa, Lord of the creatures, praised Mahāmāyā with uttermost joy, bending his neck in modesty. (11)” (Translation by Kooij)

Reference: Moodie, Deonnie. *The Making of a Modern Temple and a Hindu City: Kalighat and Kolkata*. Oxford University Press, n.d.. fig.1.1

Reference: Van Kooij, Karel R.. *Tantric Teachings of the Kālikā Purāṇa*. Leiden: Brill, n.d.. p.187

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 超自然存在 (抽象的)

— 否

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 死后世界/来世的画像

— 否

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 教义的不同方面（比如，十字，三位合一，密特拉符号）
— 否

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 人类
— 否

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 超自然存在叙事
— 是

Notes: The iconology of Kālī, especially her protruding tongue, is related to her myth in the Devī Māhātmya. A demon named Raktabīja is able to reproduce himself through his blood drops, so he duplicates when wounded by Durgā on the battlefield. Summoned by Durgā, Kālī sucks blood from Raktabīja's body, defeating him after draining all his blood and eating up all of his duplicates (Devī Māhātmya 8.49-61).

Reference: Coburn, Thomas B.. Encountering the Goddess: A Translation of the Devī-māhātmya and a Study of Its Interpretation. Albany, N.Y: SUNY series in Hindu studies, n.d..

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 人类叙事
— 否

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 其他【请注明】

—其他【请注明】: The lolling tongue and four hands are made of gold.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

信念与实践

丧葬协会

这个地方是一个坟墓/埋葬地吗：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

此地是用来崇拜故人的吗：

— 否

Notes: Roy mentioned that some families hire Brahmins of Kalighat to perform ancestor rituals, such as śrāddha. According to her study, Kalighat Brahmins were known for performing simplified versions of rituals, so they could help to save time and expense of the ritual.

Reference: Basu Roy, Indrani. Kalighat, Its Impact on Socio-cultural Life of Hindus. New Delhi: Gyan Publishing House, n.d.. p.102-103, 110-112

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

此地用于处理尸体吗：

— 否

Notes: Although Kalighat Temple is not a funeral place, it is adjacent to the Sha Nagar Keoratala Burning Ghat and Keoratola Mahasashan, which offer funeral and cremation services. Because the goddess Kali is a goddess of death and destruction, the adjacency between the Kalighat temple and the funeral ground is reasonable.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

坟墓/埋葬地有共同献祭：

共同献祭是坟墓/埋葬地的主要主任死亡导致的动物/人类献祭。

— 否

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

坟墓物品在场：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

正式埋葬存在吗：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

超自然存在

至上最高之神存在：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

他们是拟人化的吗：

— 是

Notes: In Śakti tradition, goddess Kālī is considered a supreme high god. She is neither a sky nor an underworld deity, but a fierce goddess who is honored by all other gods.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

他们是天空神：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

他们是冥神（地下）

— 否

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

他们和国王/国王身份融合（王=至上之神）

— 否

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

他们君主是被认为至上之神的表现形式或是化身：

— 否

Notes: Durgā, another incarnation of Kālī, is considered related to the monarch. Durgā is the state goddess who protects the kingdom and ensures victory in battles in medieval India. In Durgā Pūjā, Kālī is also invoked to receive animal sacrifices.

Reference: Sarkar, Bihani. *Heroic Shāktism: The Cult of Durgā in Ancient Indian Kingship*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, n.d..

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

他们和精英有亲属关系吗：

— 否

Notes: On the contrary, goddess Kālī is originally associated non-elite people who are peripheral to a society, such as robbers and thieves. In the Gauḍavaho, she is worshipped by Śabarās, who are tribals marginal in a Hindu society. In the Bhāgavata Purāṇa, Kālī is worshiped by a band of thieves who perform human sacrifices.

Reference: Kinsley, David R.. "Kālī". In *Encountering Kālī: In the Margins, at the Center, in the West*, edited by Rachel McDermott Fell and Jeffrey J. Kripal. Berkeley, Calif.: University of California Press, n.d.. p.24

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

他们是其他种类的忠诚或者和精英关联吗：

— 是

Notes: Military goddess

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

他们毫无疑问是好的：

— 否

Notes: Kālī is an ambiguous figure in the Hindu tradition. On the one hand, she is a fierce goddess who violently consumes blood and flesh, and is always associated with death and destruction. On the other hand, she is the mother goddess who grants boons and protection to her devotees. The contradiction and ambiguity in her character indicate the complexity of the historical development of Kālī. Elites such as Ramakrishna and Hāldār Brahmins who manage the Kalighat Temple contribute to the domestication of this ferocious mother goddess.

Reference: Gupta, Sanjukta. "The Domestication of a Goddess: Caraṇa-tīrtha Kālīghāṭ, the Mahāpīṭha of Kālī". In *Encountering Kālī: In the Margins, at the Center, in the West*, edited by Rachel Fell McDermott and Jeffrey J. Kripal. Berkeley, Calif.: University of California Press, 2003.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

他们是别的：

— 其他【请注明】: Goddess Kālī is often identified with, or considered an aspect of other goddesses, such as Cāmuṇḍā, Durgā, Vindhyavāsini, and Caṇḍī.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

最高至上之神在此处和生灵交流：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

以前的人类灵魂存在：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

人类灵魂和此处的生灵沟通吗：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

非人类超自然存在存在：

— 是

Notes: In addition to the deities worshipped as icons, there are also guardian deities and semi-gods who are invoked to the ritual site to ensure the success of rituals. Bāṭukas, Yoginīs, Kṣetrapālas, and Ganapati are present during the animal sacrifice. Although they are unperceivable, blood and flesh offerings should also be presented to them.

Reference: Samanta, Suchitra. "The "self-animal" and Divine Digestion: Goat Sacrifice to the Goddess Kali in Bengal". *The Journal of Asian Studies* 53, no. 3 (January 1, 2003): 779-803.

<https://doi.org/10.2307/2059730>. p.789

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

人类灵魂可以被看到：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

人类灵魂可以被物理性的感知：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

非人类灵魂在此处和生灵交流吗：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

混合人类-神圣的存在在场：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

混合人类-神圣的存在和此地的生灵交流：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

超自然存在/至上之神以异国雕像的形式展现吗：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

异教雕像可见吗：

— 是

Notes: The statue of Kālī is placed in the inner sanctum of the main temple. The body of Kālī is covered with Saree, but her face, hands, and feet are visible. Devotees line up to circumambulate her to take a full view of the statue. Alternatively, people can also see her face in the Natmondir.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

异教的雕像是隐藏的吗

— 否

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

超自然互动

超自然监视存在：

一是

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 规定遵守的超自然监视：

一是

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 超自然存在在意或者期待祭品：

一是

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 解放：

一否

Notes: Although liquor is a common Tantric oblation, there is no mention of using liquor in the Kālī worship in Kalighat as far as I have observed. Kālikā Purāṇa prohibits Brahmins from offering liquor to goddess Kālī. The Kālikā Purāṇa 67.51 states that “after offering liquor (madya), a Brahmin falls from Brahminhood.”

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 食物供给：

一是【请注明】：Sweets, fruits, milk and cooked dishes are pleasing to Kālī. These offerings can be bought from shops and vendors around the temple.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 献祭动物：

一是【请注明】：Goat sacrifice and buffalo sacrifice

Notes: Goat sacrifice is performed daily in Kalighat. A goat is sacrificed every day around 12:30 pm for the midday meal of goddess Kālī. Buffalo sacrifice is performed during Durga Puja. Animal sacrifices are performed in the Harkath Tala, which can be “seen” by Kālī from the main temple.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 献祭人类：

— 否

Notes: Although human sacrifice is prescribed in the Kālikā Purāṇa (67.18-19, 46, 73-91), it is not performed in Kalighat as far as I have observed.

Reference: Van Kooij, Karel R.. *Tantric Teachings of the Kālikā Purāṇa*. Leiden: Brill, n.d.. p.157-178

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 祭品：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 日常生活物品

— 是【请注明】：Saree, Rupees, coins and flowers can be offered to Kālī.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 其他：

— 其他【请注明】：None

↳ 超自然存在在意性问题：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 超自然存在在意或者要求适当的宗教仪式：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 超自然存在在意或者要求仪式的演绎：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 超自然存在在意或者要求地方的维护：

—是

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 超自然存在在意或者要求个人卫生：

—是

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 超自然存在在意荣誉宣誓：

—是

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 其他：

—其他【请注明】：None

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

访客能和上帝或者超自然存在沟通吗：

—是

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 访客能和上帝沟通吗：

—是

Notes: Visitors communicate with Kālī by taking darśana of the goddess. Darśana, which means vision, refers to the visual perception of the sacred. On the one hand, devotees behold the image, honoring the goddess with their sight. On the other hand, devotees are also seen by the deity, thus receiving the auspicious sight of the goddess.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 访客能和其他超自然存在沟通吗：

—否

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

仪式与表演

牺牲、祭品、和维护

此处有献祭表现

— 是

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

有动物献祭吗：

— 是【请注明】：Goat sacrifices are performed daily in Kalighat Temple, and buffalo sacrifices are performed during Durga Puja.

Notes: Goat sacrifice, namely pathaboli in Bengali, is performed daily in the temple as a living tradition. A goat is sacrificed every day around 12:30 pm for the midday meal of goddess Kālī. In addition to this regular daily sacrifice, more goats are immolated if devotees come to make this offering. Buffalos are also offered during Durga Puja. The sacrifice is performed in the Harkath Tala, the sacred sacrificial pavilion in which two alters are established side by side. The tall one is for buffalo sacrifice and the short one is for goat sacrifice.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

有人类献祭吗：

— 否

Notes: Although human sacrifice is prescribed in the Kālikā Purāṇa (67.18-19, 46, 73-91), it is not performed in Kalighat as far as I have observed.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

牺牲的人以某种方式相关联：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

有自我牺牲展现吗：

— 否

Notes: Although Kālikā Purāṇa (67.5, 67.155-162) enjoins offering blood drained from one's own body, self-sacrifice is not performed in Kalighat Temple as far as I have observed. However, I find that

devotees perform ritual actions that symbolize self-sacrifice. Devotees usually touch sacrificial altars with their heads, as if they are offering their heads just as offering a goat's head. People also crack coconuts as substitutes for their own heads and pour coconut water over sacrificial altars. These acts analogous to self-sacrifice show their devotion and complete surrender to goddess Kālī.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

物质祭品存在吗：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 物质祭品是强制的吗：

— 否

Notes: Material offerings are not mandatory, but are highly recommended. Vendors around the temple also persuade visitors to buy the offerings.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 物质祭品包括值钱物品吗：

— 否

Notes: Most material offerings including flowers, sweets, and radishes can be easily purchased from vendors around the temple. The prices are cheap according to my experience in 2017 and 2019. For example, a garland made with red joba flowers (China rose) costs 10 rupees. A radish, which is considered pleasing to the goddess, costs 15 rupees. The only exception is the goat. In 2017, the price of a live goat is around Rs 500-600 per kg. Most sacrificial goats are very small, appearing to be no more than 10 kilograms. An interlocutor I interviewed in 2019 told me that she thought only rich people perform goat sacrifice, because a live goat is quite expensive.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 物质祭品包括日常生活物品：

— 是

Notes: Flowers and sweets are very common in the daily life of Hindus. These substances are used not only in temple worship, but also in daily worship at home.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 物质祭品是否埋葬在此处（在贮藏处）：

— 否

Notes: Edibles such as sweets are distributed to devotees or consumed by temple workers. Withered Flowers are cleared up everyday in the afternoon. Coconuts are usually taken away by devotees after pouring the coconut water over the sacrificial altars.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 其他

— 其他【请注明】: Devotees offer also rupee notes and coins to Goddess Kālī when they circumambulate the inner sanctum, although they know money finally goes to the priest who serves in the sanctum.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

参加敬神/献祭活动是强制的吗：

— 否

Notes: The worship and sacrifice to Kālī are considered kāmya rituals (optional rituals that people perform from desire of benefit).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

此处的维护表现吗：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 是规定必须的吗：

— 是

Notes: The Kālīghāt Temple Committee (KTC) is responsible for the maintenance of Kalighat Temple. The employees involved in maintenance should be paid by the KTC with the income of the temple.

Reference: Moodie, Deonnie. *The Making of a Modern Temple and a Hindu City: Kalighat and Kolkata*. Oxford University Press, n.d.. p.90-92

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 有清扫吗（为了维护）：

— 是

Notes: As I have observed in 2017 and 2019, cleansing is conducted every afternoon. Temple

workers cleanse the floor with water, and remove withered flowers and other rubbish from the temple.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

是否有定期维修/重建：

— 是

Notes: According to the directive issued by the High Court of India in 2006, the West Bengal Tourism Development Corporation allots three crore rupees for the repair works of Kalighat Temple.

Reference: Moodie, Deonnie. *The Making of a Modern Temple and a Hindu City: Kalighat and Kolkata*. Oxford University Press, n.d.. p.121-122

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

是否由固定工作人员进行维护

— 是

Notes: In addition to permanent staff employed by the temple, children who live around Kalighat Temple also help to do some cleaning work. They are compensated by food oblations and coins placed on the altars.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

其他

— 其他【请注明】：None

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

朝圣与节日

朝圣是否存在：

— 是

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

朝圣有多严格：

— 可选 (常见)

Notes: Kalighat Temple is a pilgrimage site for śāktas (the worshipper of goddesses who are śaktis in Hindu tradition). According to my interviews, many devotees from West Bengal,

Bihar, and Assam come to honor Kālī in Kalighat.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 朝圣是构建/建立场所的主要原因：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 朝圣到此处与重要的人生事件有关联吗：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 到此处的朝圣是否包括跟随建成的路线（道路）

— 否

Notes: The official website of Kalighat Temple offers a few tour packages of temple tour. However, these routes are not mandatory for pilgrimage.

Reference: Kalighat Kali Temple. "Official Website of Kalighat Temple". Kalighat Kali Temple, n.d.. <https://kalighatkalitemple.com/>.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

此处是宴席的场所：

— 是

Notes: Vegetarian food is freely distributed in the temple in the afternoons. It is often rice, dal, or other curry dishes placed on a leaf plate. Devotees can also buy cooked mutton as prasāda, the food first presented to the goddess Kālī, and then distributed to devotees as the grace of Kālī. Moreover, hundreds of beggars around Kalighat Temple are fed as forms of god Viṣṇu.

Reference: Moodie, Deonnie. *The Making of a Modern Temple and a Hindu City: Kalighat and Kolkata*. Oxford University Press, n.d.. p.15, 86

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 宴席是否和在此处表演的崇拜/献祭活动有关：

— 是

Notes: The food distributed in feasting is considered prasāda—the food consumed first by the goddess. To prepare the midday meal for Kālī, the temple kitchen cooks rice, vegetable curries, and mutton curries every noon. A portion of the food will be offered to Kālī, and the

rest of the food will be shared by priests, temple workers, and other visitors.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 宴席是由建造/维护此地的同一个团体赞助：

— 是

Notes: The cost of feasting is paid by the sevāyets (or shebait in Bengali, temple proprietor), who manage the temple in turn. Part of the cost is covered by donation.

Reference: Moodie, Deonnie. *The Making of a Modern Temple and a Hindu City: Kalighat and Kolkata*. Oxford University Press, n.d.. p.15

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 牧师

— 是

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 地方精英

— 是

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 私人贡献

— 是

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 其他

— 其他【请注明】：Half of the monetary offerings received by the temple is given to sevāyets, who pay for feasts and other services in the temple.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 宴席是否在此处特定的地方进行：

— 是【请注明】：The distribution of food usually occurs in front of the Harkath Tala in the southern part of the temple.

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE
Region: West Bengal

节日展示吗：

—是

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE
Region: West Bengal

节日的频次

—请注明: Durga Puja and Kali Puja are yearly festivals.

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE
Region: West Bengal

社会的所有成员都参与节日吗：

—所有成员

Notes: The festivals are open to everyone including foreigners and outcastes.

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE
Region: West Bengal

节日是此处建筑物/装饰的一个决定因素吗：

—否

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE
Region: West Bengal

平均来说，多少参与者会在此处聚集：

—数字: Thousands of people gather in Kalighat during the festivals.

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE
Region: West Bengal

宴席是节日的一部分吗：

—是

Notes: More devotees come to enjoy the prasāda of Kālī during Durgā Pūjā and Kālī Pūjā.

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE
Region: West Bengal

|

↳ 食物消耗是否限定于一定的人口

- 精英
- 非精英
- 宗教人士

Notes: Food consumption is open to the public. There is no particular limitation regarding who is qualified to enjoy the feasting.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

占卜与治愈

有占卜展示吗：

- 否

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

治愈是否在此处展现/实践：

- 否

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

仪式在这个地方发生吗：

仪式是一个或多个人为了宗教仪式而明显制定的行为。

- 是

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 大型仪式在此处进行吗：

- 是

Notes: Goat sacrifice is performed daily in the temple. During the Durga Puja, people also sacrifice buffalos in the Harkath Tala. In the evening, devotees convene to perform the evening ārtī, in which devotees worship the goddess with a lamp, chant Kālī's name and sing songs in praise of Kālī.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 小型仪式在这里进行吗：

- 是

Notes: Personal worship happens throughout the day. Devotees can make offerings to and take darśana of the goddess Kālī anytime except when the inner sanctum is closed. People are not allowed to enter the inner sanctum from 2pm to 4pm, when goddess Kālī enjoys her lunch and rests.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

平均有多少参与者参加大型仪式：

—请注明: More than 50 people are present during daily worships. More than hundred people gather for festivals such as Durga Puja and Kali Puja.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

仪式多久发生一次：

—请注明: All of these rituals are performed daily.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

有正统性检查吗：

—是

Notes: The violence involved in animal sacrifice apparently conflicts with the doctrine of non-violence upheld by mainstream Hinduism. To account for this conflict, priests in Kalighat Temple are inclined to de-emphasize the sacrificial violence, interpreting the animal sacrifice as a devotional practice to please the goddess.

有正位检查 (orthopraxy checks) 吗：

—是

Notes: Most rituals performed in inner sanctums are quite standardized as they are supervised by purohit, but it is not the case of animal sacrifice. A standardized procedure of animal sacrifice is prescribed in ritual manuals, such as Śrīśrīkālīpūjā Paddhati and Purohita Darpaṇa. However, most pāṇḍās perform the ritual in simplified ways, and the ritual performance varies depending on the personal preference of pāṇḍās.

是否存在共时实践：

—是

Notes: During the evening worship, devotees chant the name of Kālī or Kālī Mā (Mother Kālī) synchronically. During the animal sacrifice, women will utter together the sound of ulu (ululi in Sanskrit, ulu dhvani in Bengali), which is a high-pitched sound produced by the rapid back and forth movement of the tongue. The ulu dhvani is considered an outcry indicative of auspiciousness.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 仪式中使用麻醉剂吗：

— 否

Notes: Although liquor is a common Tantric oblation, it is not employed in the rituals in Kalighat temple as far as I have observed.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

机构和经文

宗教专家

宗教专家是否展现/掌控此地：

宗教专家是在人口群体中主要职责不是关心子女和手工生产，而是维护宗教图景和族群文化。

— 是

Notes: Three groups of specialists are present in Kalighat. Sevāyets, or shebaites in Bengali, are temple proprietors who manage daily worship and other affairs in the temple. All sevāyets in Kalighat are male decedents of Bhavānīdās Cakravarti, who was the first sevāyet of Kalighat Temple. These Sevāyets belonging to the Haldar family inherited the rights of managing the temple from their ancestors. More than one thousand sevāyets take turns (pālā) to manage the temple. Purohitas are priests who are in charge of daily worship in the inner sanctum of Kalighat temple. Pāṇḍās are ritual specialists who do not have official positions in Kalighat. They roam about in the temple to find devotees who need ritual service. They guide visitors through worship and prayers in various shrines, and are paid with dakṣiṇā (ritual fee) by visitors. Most pāṇḍās are not well-trained in Sanskrit and they only perform simple versions of rituals. Pāṇḍās also perform goat sacrifice for those who want to offer a goat. As far as I have observed, they only perform the purification section prescribed by the ritual manual Purohit Darpan, and then they hand over the goat victims to Bāgdi people, who are in charge of immolating the animal. Three groups of specialists are present in Kalighat. Sevāyets, or shebaites in Bengali, are temple proprietors who manage daily worship and other affairs in the temple. All sevāyets in Kalighat are male decedents of Bhavānīdās Cakravarti, who was the first sevāyet of Kalighat Temple. These Sevāyets belonging to the Haldar family inherited the rights of managing the temple from their ancestors. More than one thousand sevāyets take turns (pālā) to the manage the temple. Purohitas are priests who are in charge of daily worship in the inner sanctum of Kalighat temple. Pāṇḍās are ritual specialists who do not have official positions in Kalighat. They roam about in the temple to find devotees who need ritual service. They guide visitors through worship and prayers in various shrines, and are paid with dakṣiṇā (ritual fee) by visitors. Most of pāṇḍās are not well-trained in Sanskrit and they only perform simple versions of rituals. Pāṇḍās also perform goat sacrifice for those who want to offer a goat. As far as I have observed, they only perform the purification section prescribed by the ritual manual Purohit Darpan, and then they hand over the goat victims to Bāgdi people, who are in charge of immolating the animal. Although pāṇḍās are called "sāthī Brahmins", some of them are born in lower castes or even of Muslim origin. They are notorious for cheating, overcharging, and other misconducts such as sexual harassment.

Reference: Moodie, Deonnie. *The Making of a Modern Temple and a Hindu City: Kalighat and Kolkata*. Oxford University Press, n.d.. p.140-144

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 全职

— 是

Notes: Sevāyets manage Kalighat Temple through a mechanism of pālā (turns), so each of

them is only allocated a few days or even a few hours per year. Pāṇḍās stay in the temple to find customers for as long as they want. Pāṇḍās stay in the temple to find customers as long as they want.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 兼任

一是

Notes: Sevāyets manage Kalighat Temple through a mechanism of pālā (turns), so each of them is only allocated a few days or even a few hours per year. Pāṇḍās stay in the temple to find customers for as long as they want.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 宗教专家是否特定性别

一是

Notes: All the ritual specialists are male.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 宗教专家是否特定种族

一是

Notes: Brahmin priests must be Hindus. The temple workers in charge of immolating sacrificial victims are Bāṅḍī people, who are tribals in eastern India.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 宗教专家是否属于特定阶级/

一是

Notes: Theoretically, priests must be Brahmins since only Brahmins can ensure the purity of ritual. However, in reality, some of the pāṇḍās are born in lower castes or even of Muslim origin.

Reference: Moodie, Deonnie. *The Making of a Modern Temple and a Hindu City: Kalighat and Kolkata*. Oxford University Press, n.d.. p.141

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 宗教专家是否致力于生活的地方

一是

Notes: Sevāyets are dedicated to Kalighat, but purohitas and the pāṇḍās are not necessarily

affiliated with the temple.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 宗教专家是否在等级制度中分层：

— 是

Notes: Sevāyets are highest in the hierarchy as they inherit legitimacy from their family lineage. Purohits, though inferior to Sevāyets, are prestigious ritualists who are qualified to serve the images in the inner shrine. In contrast, Pāṇḍās are the lowest in the hierarchy, and are notorious for cheating, pickpocketing, and sexual harassment. Most Pāṇḍās do not consider their job decent or lucrative.

Reference: Moodie, Deonnie. *The Making of a Modern Temple and a Hindu City: Kalighat and Kolkata*. Oxford University Press, n.d.. p.140-142

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 是由这等级区分进入这空间的入口

— 是

Notes: Pāṇḍās are not allowed to enter the inner sanctum, since they are considered not as pure as purohits.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

此地给宗教专家收纳了生活空间吗：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

这个地方被用作宗教专家的训练用吗：

— 否

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

有正式的机构来维护此地吗：

由宗教社群或政治领袖授权的机构

— 是

Notes: Two institutions are responsible for the maintenance of Kalighat Temple: the Kalighat Temple Committee (KTC) and the Executive Committee of the Council of Shebaites (ECCS). The KTC is in charge of the overall management and financial issues of the temple. The KTC pays the temple employees

with the half of temple income, and ensures that the other half of the income is distributed to the sevāyets based on their pālās (turns). According to the ruling issued by the Supreme Court of India in 1961, the KTS should include 5 sevāyets and 6 Hindu public representatives. However, in reality, the KTC today is comprised of sevāyets alone . The ECCS is in charge of the daily worship and allocating pālās to sevāyets. The ECCS is subject to the KTC.

Reference: Moodie, Deonnie. *The Making of a Modern Temple and a Hindu City: Kalighat and Kolkata*. Oxford University Press, n.d.. p.90-93, 147

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

官僚机构

有官方官僚机构在此处出现吗：

官僚机构包括一个主要涉及物质财富的会计和规则维护的等级制度。

—是

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 官僚机构永久存在吗

—是

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 官僚机构暂时/季节性存在吗

—否

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

这个地方控制经济资源吗（土地，物品，工具）：

—否

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

公共事业

这个地方是否可以作为社区服务的场所：

—是

Notes: Kalighat can be considered a charitable institution to some extent, as hundred of beggars who gather around Kalighat are fed by the temple funding every day.

Reference: Moodie, Deonnie. *The Making of a Modern Temple and a Hindu City: Kalighat and Kolkata*. Oxford University Press, n.d.. p.15, 86

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 公共食物分发和/或储藏
— 是

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 公民职能的地方（人口普查，选举，其他）
— 否

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 司法实践的地方（审判，处决等）。
— 否

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 水管理功能
— 否

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 交通网络的部分
— 否

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

↳ 其他
— 其他【请注明】: None

文字/经文

此处是否保存了非宗教文字：

经济文档、记录等。

— 否

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

是否有与这个地方相关的经文

— 否

Notes: Although most ritual manuals circulated around Kalighat Temple attribute their scriptural authority to Kālikā Purāṇa, Kalighat is not mentioned in the Kālikā Purāṇa.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 19 BCE - 21 CE

Region: West Bengal

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Kalighat Temple, Basu Roy, Indrani. *Kalighat, Its Impact on Socio-cultural Life of Hindus*. New Delhi: Gyan Publishing House, n.d..

Reference: Kalighat Temple, Moodie, Deonnie. *The Making of a Modern Temple and a Hindu City: Kalighat and Kolkata*. Oxford University Press, n.d..

Reference: Kalighat Temple, Samanta, Suchitra. "The "self-animal" and Divine Digestion: Goat Sacrifice to the Goddess Kali in Bengal". *The Journal of Asian Studies* 53, no. 3 (January 1, 2003): 779-803. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2059730>.

Reference: Kalighat Temple, Van Kooij, Karel R.. *Tantric Teachings of the Kālikā Purāṇa*. Leiden: Brill, n.d..

Reference: Kalighat Temple, Coburn, Thomas B.. *Encountering the Goddess: A Translation of the Devī-māhātmya and a Study of Its Interpretation*. Albany, N.Y.: SUNY series in Hindu studies, n.d..

Reference: Kalighat Temple, Sarkar, Bihani. *Heroic Shāktism: The Cult of Durgā in Ancient Indian Kingship*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, n.d..

Reference: Kalighat Temple, Kinsley, David R.. "Kālī". In *Encountering Kālī: In the Margins, at the Center, in the West*, edited by Rachel McDermott Fell and Jeffrey J. Kripal. Berkeley, Calif.: University of California Press, n.d..

Reference: Kalighat Temple, Gupta, Sanjukta. "The Domestication of a Goddess: Caraṇa-tīrtha Kālīghāṭ, the Mahāpīṭha of Kālī". In *Encountering Kālī: In the Margins, at the Center, in the West*, edited by Rachel Fell McDermott and Jeffrey J. Kripal. Berkeley, Calif.: University of California Press, 2003.

Reference: Kalighat Temple, Shastri N., B., ed.. *Kālikāpurāṇa: Text, Introduction & Translation in English*. Edited by B. Shastri N.. Delhi: Nag Publishers, n.d..

Entry/Answer References

Reference: 否, Basu Roy, Indrani. *Kalighat, Its Impact on Socio-cultural Life of Hindus*. New Delhi: Gyan Publishing House, n.d.. p.p.13, p.pp.1-14, p.pp.15-19, p.3, p.2-3, p.102-103, 110-112

Reference: 是, Moodie, Deonnie. *The Making of a Modern Temple and a Hindu City: Kalighat and Kolkata*. Oxford University Press, n.d.. p.49-57, p.172, n.7, fig.1.1, p.90-92, p.121-122, p.15, p.15, 86, p.141, p.140-144, p.140-142, p.90-93, 147, p.15, 86, p.143

Reference: 是, Samanta, Suchitra. "The "self-animal" and Divine Digestion: Goat Sacrifice to the Goddess Kali in Bengal". *The Journal of Asian Studies* 53, no. 3 (January 1, 2003): 779-803.
<https://doi.org/10.2307/2059730>. p.789

Reference: 是, Van Kooij, Karel R.. *Tantric Teachings of the Kālikā Purāṇa*. Leiden: Brill, n.d.. p.187, p.157-178

Reference: 是, Coburn, Thomas B.. *Encountering the Goddess: A Translation of the Devī-māhātmya and a Study of Its Interpretation*. Albany, N.Y.: SUNY series in Hindu studies, n.d..

Reference: 否, Sarkar, Bihani. *Heroic Shāktism: The Cult of Durgā in Ancient Indian Kingship*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, n.d..

Reference: 否, Kinsley, David R.. "Kālī". In *Encountering Kālī: In the Margins, at the Center, in the West*, edited by Rachel McDermott Fell and Jeffrey J. Kripal. Berkeley, Calif.: University of California Press, n.d.. p.24

Reference: 否, Gupta, Sanjukta. "The Domestication of a Goddess: Caraṇa-tīrtha Kālighāṭ, the Mahāpīṭha of Kālī". In *Encountering Kālī: In the Margins, at the Center, in the West*, edited by Rachel Fell McDermott and Jeffrey J. Kripal. Berkeley, Calif.: University of California Press, 2003.

Reference: 否, Kalighat Kali Temple. "Official Website of Kalighat Temple". Kalighat Kali Temple, n.d..
<https://kalighatkalitemple.com/>.